

Three years post-pandemic of SARS-CoV-2: Insights from a Bulgarian online survey

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Abstract

Beyond its medical implications, the COVID-19 pandemic precipitated widespread psychological distress, with numerous studies reporting increases in anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues across diverse populations worldwide. This study examined the evolution of perceptions, emotions, and coping strategies from the initial 2020 outbreak to the post-crisis period in 2023 through two identical online surveys conducted among Bulgarian citizens: “How do I feel during the COVID-19 pandemic?” (2020) and “How do I feel after the COVID-19 pandemic?” (2023). The surveys utilized standardized questionnaires with 24 core questions in 2020 (n = 1,020) and 27 questions in 2023 (n = 661), distributed through digital platforms including Facebook, LinkedIn, and e-mail. Results revealed significant improvements in mental health outcomes by 2023, including enhanced mood (p < 0.001), reduced feelings of sadness and helplessness (from 12.9% to 7.7% experiencing daily symptoms), decreased financial stress (severe stress declining from 11.4% to 5.3%), and reduced unhealthy habits. Additionally, belief in conspiracy theories regarding the virus’s origins and transmission methods decreased significantly. These findings underscore the importance of ongoing monitoring and targeted mental health interventions to address the diverse psychological needs following major global crises.

Keywords

Bulgaria, COVID-19, long-term impact, online survey, pandemic perception, post-pandemic, public health, SARS-CoV-2

Introduction

The impact of crisis on mental health

Throughout recorded history, humanity has faced numerous large-scale crises, including armed conflicts,

economic collapses, natural disasters, and global health emergencies. “Nearly everyone will experience emotional and psychological distress in the immediate aftermath of a disaster or other large-scale traumatic event” (Gray et al. 2004). Each of these events has had a profound im-

pact on societies, often leaving long-term consequences on individuals' mental and emotional well-being. Among such crises, pandemics present a unique and far-reaching challenge, as they not only affect physical health and strain healthcare systems but also generate prolonged periods of uncertainty, fear, and social isolation. "Data from previous major emergencies and pandemics pointed to a likely peak in mental health problems, which was predicted to occur later than the initial peak in physical illness and also to endure for longer" (Gavin et al. 2021).

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, rapidly evolved into a global crisis affecting nearly every aspect of life. "Following its initial outbreak, it spread rapidly across the global community, prompting the World Health Organization to declare COVID-19 a global pandemic in March 2020" (Chen et al. 2021). Beyond its medical implications, the pandemic triggered widespread psychological distress, with numerous studies reporting increases in anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress, and other mental health issues across diverse populations (Xie et al. 2022). Even after patients had recovered from the illness and were successfully discharged, an additional cause for concern was the emergence of unexpected complications (Grigorov et al. 2022). The abrupt changes in daily routines, enforced social distancing, lockdown measures, and the loss of lives and livelihoods contributed to what many experts have described as a parallel "mental health pandemic." In this context, the role of psychosocial support has emerged as not only beneficial but also essential. The United Nations highlighted that the mental health of whole societies has been severely impacted by this disaster and must be addressed as a priority (Lindert et al. 2021).

Psychosocial support and mental health in times of crisis

In response to the increasing need for structured mental health interventions during emergencies, the United Nations Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC) introduced the framework of mental health and psychosocial support (MHPSS) (IASC 2021). This term encompasses "any type of local or external support aimed at protecting or promoting psychosocial well-being and/or preventing or treating mental health disorders" during crises. MHPSS approaches are multifaceted and context-sensitive, considering cultural, societal, and economic factors that shape individual and collective experiences of trauma.

During pandemics like COVID-19, psychosocial support encompasses a wide range of services, including mental health counseling, emotional first aid, stress management training, public health communication, and community-based support networks. Crucially, MHPSS interventions focus not only on clinical symptoms but also on social factors, including family dynamics, workplace stress, education, and access to healthcare. This holistic approach is particularly important in mitigating long-term psychological effects and promoting community resilience. As mentioned in other studies, mental dis-

orders are strongly connected with the fear of rejection in people's social circles – family, friends, and colleagues – because of humans' natural need for belonging to a certain group in order to be integrated and function properly as members of society (Dimitrova et al. 2020). According to the handbook, "sustainability can be enhanced when it is identified as a foundation of the approach from the beginning and considered throughout" (IASC 2021).

Acknowledging the psychological burden of COVID-19, particularly in countries with limited access to mental healthcare, is a key step toward understanding the broader consequences of the pandemic. Vulnerable groups – including healthcare workers, the elderly, young people, and individuals with pre-existing mental health conditions – require targeted support to prevent further deterioration of their mental health.

In Bulgaria, as in many other countries, the COVID-19 pandemic imposed new social norms and psychological stressors. Recognizing the need for empirical data to assess the long-term mental health consequences of the pandemic, a two-phase online survey was conducted to evaluate Bulgarian citizens' mental health and psychosocial experiences during and after the crisis. The study aimed to capture the evolution of perceptions, emotions, and coping strategies from the initial shock of the 2020 outbreak to the post-crisis period in 2023. The primary aim of the study was to compare the results of two identical online surveys conducted 3 years apart: the first titled "How do I feel during the COVID-19 pandemic?" in 2020, and the second, "How do I feel after the COVID-19 pandemic?" in 2023. By analyzing changes in self-reported mental health status, levels of emotional distress, and perceived social support, the study sought to provide insights into the longer-term psychosocial impact of the pandemic in Bulgaria.

Methods

Two questionnaires were used: the pre-pandemic (conducted in 2020) "How do I feel during the COVID-19 pandemic?" and the post-pandemic (conducted in 2023) "How do I feel after the COVID-19 pandemic?". Data collection for the first survey took place in May 2020, and its details are described elsewhere (Velikova et al. 2020). To ensure methodological consistency and comparability, the research team developed a standardized, anonymous questionnaire composed of 24 core questions from the initial 2020 survey. These questions covered areas such as emotional well-being, coping mechanisms, fears and concerns, social relationships, and perceived changes in lifestyle. Before its distribution, the survey underwent pilot testing with 20 individuals to evaluate the clarity, relevance, and comprehensibility of the questions. Based on participant feedback, three new questions were added to the 2023 survey, and minor adjustments were made to verb tenses and phrasing to reflect the retrospective nature of the follow-up study. The final 2023 version included 27 questions.

Respondents in both surveys were informed about the aim of the research, their voluntary participation, and data confidentiality prior to completing the questionnaires, and they provided informed consent by clicking the “Continue” button.

The survey was distributed electronically through widely used digital platforms, including Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, and e-mail mailing lists. Participants were Bulgarian citizens aged 18 and above. The design ensured that respondents could submit their answers only after completing all required fields, thereby maintaining the integrity and completeness of the dataset. The anonymity of the survey encouraged honest and unfiltered responses, which are essential in studies involving sensitive personal topics such as mental health.

Statistical methods

Results are presented as numbers and/or proportions. The Pearson chi-square test (Fisher’s exact test when applicable) was used to compare both surveys. Results were considered significant if $p < 0.05$ for two-sided tests. IBM SPSS Statistics v.29 was used.

Results

Demographics and occupation

A total of 1,020 respondents were recruited during the pandemic and an additional 661 respondents after the pandemic. Their characteristics are presented in Table 1. Both groups were similar in terms of sex, with a predom-

inance of females (83.8% during the pandemic and 82.2% post-pandemic). They differed significantly in their age groups ($p < 0.001$). During the pandemic, the majority of respondents were between 21 and 40 years old (71.4%), while after the pandemic, the most prevalent age group was 41–60 years old (58%). Age differences significantly influenced the likelihood of having children: respondents after the pandemic reported having offspring more often (71% compared to 61.8% during the pandemic; $p < 0.001$). The proportion of those whose children were younger than 7 years old was similar in both groups (36.8% during the pandemic and 35% post-pandemic; $p > 0.05$). Children of school age were more often reported by post-pandemic respondents (28.1% compared to 18.3% during the pandemic; $p < 0.001$). The post-pandemic group also more often reported having children above 18 years old (17.8% vs. 13.4%; $p = 0.014$).

Respondents in both surveys were asked if they had a job. A significant difference was observed in the answers ($p < 0.001$). A significantly higher proportion of respondents after the pandemic reported going to their workplaces in person (56.3% compared to 36.3% during the pandemic). The proportion of “home office” workers was similar (21.2% during the pandemic and 21.6% after the pandemic), as was the proportion on maternity or sick leave (12.5% and 11.5%, respectively). A reduction was observed among those who did not have a job due to the pandemic, as well as those who had been unemployed before the pandemic (7.3% to 0.8% and 10.2% to 2.6%, respectively).

Nearly the same proportion of respondents had jobs related to medicine and COVID-19 (27.8% and 26.3%; $p > 0.05$).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Questions	Answers	During the pandemic		After the pandemic		p
		n	%	n	%	
Sex	Male	156	15.3%	116	17.5%	0.195
	Female	855	83.8%	544	82.2%	
	Other	5	0.5%	0	0.0%	
	Prefer not to disclose	4	0.4%	2	0.3%	
Age group	< 21 years old	34	3.3%	0	0.0%	<0.001
	21–40 years old	728	71.4%	0	0.0%	
	41–60 years old	242	23.7%	384	58.0%	
	61+ years old	16	1.6%	278	42.0%	
Do you have children?	Yes	630	61.8%	470	71.0%	<0.001
	No	390	38.2%	192	29.0%	
Children under 7 years old?	Yes	375	36.8%	232	35.0%	0.473
	No	645	63.2%	430	65.0%	
Children of school age?	Yes	187	18.3%	186	28.1%	<0.001
	No	833	81.7%	476	71.9%	
Children above 18 years old?	Yes	137	13.4%	118	17.8%	0.014
	No	883	86.6%	544	82.2%	
Do you have a job?	Yes, I go to my workplace	370	36.3%	373	56.3%	<0.001
	Yes, at home (home office)	216	21.2%	143	21.6%	
	No, I do not have a job due to the pandemic	74	7.3%	5	0.8%	
	No, and I did not have a job before the pandemic	104	10.2%	17	2.6%	
	Maternity or sick leave	128	12.5%	76	11.5%	
	Other	128	12.5%	48	7.3%	
Is your job related to medicine and COVID-19 patients?	Yes	284	27.8%	174	26.3%	0.483
	No	736	72.2%	488	73.7%	

Psychological well-being

A significant increase was observed in the proportion of respondents who rarely associated flu-like symptoms (fever, cough, etc.) with COVID-19 (from 41.3% to 50.3%), as shown in Table 2. However, the proportion of respondents who actively associated these symptoms with COVID-19

also increased (from 29.8% to 37.2%). In contrast, a decrease in the proportion of respondents who tried not to think about this was noted (from 28.9% to 12.5%). In general, a significant change was observed ($p < 0.001$).

A significant decrease was recorded in the proportion of respondents who followed information channels about the pandemic either all the time or for a limited amount

Table 2. Psychological well-being of the respondents.

Questions	Answers	During the pandemic		After the pandemic		p
		n	%	n	%	
If you do not feel well and experience symptoms like fever, cough, etc., do you associate them with COVID-19?	Usually yes	304	29.8	246	37.2	<0.001
	No, rarely	421	41.3	333	50.3	
	I try not to think about this	295	28.9	83	12.5	
Do you follow the information channels about the pandemic (TV, social media, etc.)? / 2023 Do you continue to follow...	Yes, but limited	572	56.1	343	51.8	<0.001
	Yes, all the time	246	24.1	66	10.0	
	No, I avoid such information	202	19.8	253	38.2	
Do you find yourself experiencing feelings of sadness, helplessness, despair, or hopelessness more often than before?	Yes, every day	132	12.9	51	7.7	<0.001
	Yes, sometimes	422	41.4	240	36.3	
	Rarely or not at all	466	45.7	371	56.0	
Do you find yourself becoming more irritable and getting angry more easily than before?	Yes	389	38.1	170	25.7	<0.001
	No	436	42.7	341	51.5	
	I am not sure	195	19.1	151	22.8	
Do you have a strong fear that you or someone close to you could become ill?	Yes, I feel a very strong fear	82	8.0	65	9.8	0.001
	Yes, but sometimes	237	23.2	165	24.9	
	Yes, but I try not to think about it	382	37.5	186	28.1	
	Very rare or never	319	31.3	246	37.2	
Do you experience stress due to current or potential financial problems related to the pandemic?	No	456	44.7	437	66.0	<0.001
	Yes, a mild stress	448	43.9	190	28.7	
	Yes, severe stress	116	11.4	35	5.3	
Have your family relationships changed? In what direction?	Yes, towards unity	223	21.9	109	16.5	0.035
	Yes, to misunderstanding	87	8.5	54	8.2	
	I don't think they have changed	605	59.3	434	65.6	
	I am not sure	105	10.3	65	9.8	
Do you miss your family and friends? / Do you meet your family and friends more frequently?	Yes, although we keep in touch online / we were in touch online during the pandemic	718	70.4	310	46.8	<0.001
	Yes, although we haven't stopped meeting each other	112	11.0	247	37.3	
	No, we keep in touch online only	190	18.6	105	15.9	
Do you have someone to talk to if something is bothering you?	Yes	866	84.9	572	86.4	0.393
	No	154	15.1	90	13.6	
Do you feel you have a professional need for psychological support for you and your family during/after the pandemic?	Yes	212	20.8	130	19.6	0.568
	No	808	79.2	532	80.4	
Did you increase any unhealthy habits during the pandemic?	Yes	706	69.2	370	55.9	<0.001
	No	314	30.8	292	44.1	
Alcohol consumption	Yes	149	14.6	64	9.7	0.003
	No	871	85.4	598	90.3	
Cigarette smoking	Yes	184	18.0	74	11.2	<0.001
	No	836	82.0	588	88.8	
Drug use	Yes	15	1.5	3	0.5	0.048
	No	1005	98.5	659	99.5	
Overeating	Yes	313	30.7	144	21.8	<0.001
	No	707	69.3	518	78.2	
Lack of physical activity	Yes	572	56.1	298	45.0	<0.001
	No	448	43.9	364	55.0	
Other	Yes	19	1.9	8	1.2	0.297
	No	1001	98.1	654	98.8	
Are you spending more time on your hobbies? Have you taken up new hobbies or increased activities such as reading or other pastimes?	No	479	47.0	220	33.2	<0.001
	Yes	398	39.0	294	44.4	
	I am not sure	143	14.0	148	22.4	

Questions	Answers	During the pandemic		After the pandemic		p
		n	%	n	%	
Does it scare you that there is no specific treatment and prevention? / Does it scare you that there is still no specific treatment, despite ongoing drug trials?	Yes	492	48.2	233	35.2	<0.001
	No	370	36.3	332	50.2	
	I am not sure	158	15.5	97	14.7	
Are you tired of staying at home more? / Were you tired of staying at home more often?	Yes, but I'm coping with it	502	49.2	313	47.3	<0.001
	Yes, and I don't handle it	85	8.3	31	4.7	
	No, but I don't know how long	188	18.4	61	9.2	
	No, not at all	245	24.0	257	38.8	
Do you want to become infected so the pandemic "passes" more quickly? / Was there a point when you stopped protecting yourself from the virus so the pandemic would "pass" more quickly?	Yes	40	3.9	108	16.3	<0.001
	I am not sure	208	20.4	97	14.7	
	No	772	75.7	457	69.0	
Have you had sleep disturbances in recent weeks?	Yes	228	22.4	113	17.1	0.021
	Yes, worsened from before	142	13.9	88	13.3	
	No	650	63.7	461	69.6	

of time (from 56.1% to 51.8% for all the time and from 24.1% to 10% for a limited amount of time), along with an increase in the proportion of those who avoided such information (from 19.8% to 38.2%) ($p < 0.001$).

A significant improvement in mood was observed ($p < 0.001$). The proportion of respondents who felt sadness, helplessness, despair, or hopelessness decreased (from 12.9% to 7.7% every day and from 41.4% to 36.3% sometimes), while the proportion of those who rarely or did not experience such feelings increased (from 45.7% to 56%).

Respondents were asked if they had become more irritable or prone to anger. A significant decrease was observed in the proportion of respondents who answered "yes" (from 38.1% to 25.7%), along with an increase in those answering "no" (from 42.7% to 51.5%) ($p < 0.001$).

The fear that respondents themselves or someone close to them might contract the disease decreased significantly in the post-pandemic period ($p = 0.001$). An increase was observed in the proportion of those who experienced such fear very rarely or never (from 31.3% to 37.2%).

Stress related to current or future financial problems due to the pandemic decreased significantly ($p < 0.001$), from 43.9% to 28.7% for mid-level stress and from 11.4% to 5.3% for severe stress. An increase was observed in the proportion of respondents who reported no stress (from 44.7% to 66%).

During the pandemic, 59.3% of respondents reported that their family relationships remained unchanged, while 65.6% in the second survey reported the same ($p = 0.035$). A decrease was observed in the proportion of individuals whose relationships shifted toward unity (from 21.9% to 16.5%). The proportion of worsened relationships remained relatively the same (8.5% and 8.2%, respectively).

Respondents were asked during the pandemic, "Do you miss your family and friends?" and this question was modified after the pandemic to "Do you meet your family and friends more frequently?" A significant change was observed toward an increase in in-person meetings (from 11% to 37.3%) and a decrease in online contacts (from 70.4% to 46.8%). Nearly the same proportion of

respondents remained separated, maintaining online contact only (18.6% and 15.9%, respectively). The majority of respondents in both surveys reported having someone to talk to if something was bothering them (84.9% and 86.4%, respectively).

No significant change was observed in response to the question "Do you feel you have a professional need for psychological support for you and your family during/after the pandemic?" About one-fifth in both surveys responded positively (20.8% and 19.6%, respectively). Post-pandemic respondents were asked whether they had sought psychological help. One in ten (10.4%) confirmed, and almost the same proportion were considering such help (9.7%).

A significant decline in unhealthy habits that spread during the pandemic was observed ($p < 0.001$). During the pandemic, 69.2% of respondents reported an increase in these bad habits, which decreased to 55.9% in the post-pandemic period and remained at 55.9% thereafter. The most prevalent bad habit was a lack of physical activity, which was common among 56.1% of participants during the pandemic and 45% in the post-pandemic survey ($p < 0.001$). Other negative habits that decreased significantly were overeating (30.7% and 21.87%, respectively; $p < 0.001$), cigarette smoking (18% and 11.2%, respectively; $p < 0.001$), alcohol consumption (14.6% and 9.7%, respectively; $p = 0.004$), and drug use (1.5% and 0.5%, respectively; $p = 0.048$).

After the pandemic, respondents started spending significantly more time on their hobbies (39% and 44.4%, respectively); however, there was an increase in the proportion of those who were uncertain about changes in their engagement with hobbies ($p < 0.001$).

Respondents were asked during the pandemic, "Does it scare you that there is no specific treatment and prevention?" and this question was modified afterward to "Does it scare you that there is still no specific treatment, even though there are drug trials?" A significant decrease was observed in the proportion of respondents who reported being scared (from 48.2% to 35.2%), along with an in-

crease in the number of respondents who claimed not to be scared (from 36.3% to 50.2%) ($p < 0.001$).

In the post-pandemic period, a significantly greater proportion of respondents reported that they had wished to “get” the virus themselves in order for the pandemic to “pass” more quickly (from 3.9% to 16.3%) ($p < 0.001$). During the same period, significantly fewer respondents reported suffering from sleep disturbances (from 22.4% to 17.1%) ($p = 0.021$).

Myths about the pandemic

The belief that the virus was artificially engineered decreased significantly from 2020 to 2023, while the number of people who did not believe in this conspiracy theory increased ($p < 0.001$). The perception that the virus was spread via 5G or other methods to enhance its transmission also showed a clear reduction in belief from 2020 to 2023, with a larger proportion of respondents in 2023 rejecting this idea ($p < 0.001$).

Both surveys indicated that respondents felt well-informed about the COVID-19 pandemic and anti-epidemic measures (Table 3).

Table 3. Beliefs and self-reported awareness about SARS-CoV-2 over time.

Questions	Answers	During the pandemic		After the pandemic		p
		n	%	n	%	
Do you think SARS-CoV-2 was artificially created?	Yes	411	40.3	198	29.9	<0.001
	No	343	33.6	290	43.8	
	I am not sure	266	26.1	174	26.3	
Do you think SARS-CoV-2 is spreading via 5G and other methods that increase its transmission?	Yes	41	4.0	11	1.7	<0.001
	No	854	83.7	629	95.0	
	I am not sure	125	12.3	22	3.3	
Do you feel well informed about the COVID-19 pandemic and anti-epidemic measures?	Yes	756	74.1	493	74.5	0.758
	Yes, but not enough	208	20.4	138	20.8	
	No, not at all	56	5.5	31	4.7	

After the pandemic

Three additional questions were added to the post-pandemic survey. Fig. 1 presents the responses to the question, “Did you get sick from COVID-19?” Almost half of the respondents (45.5%) had a test result confirming infection, and 22.4% indicated that they had contracted COVID-19 more than once. In total, more than two-thirds had confirmed COVID-19 infection (67.9%). About 18.2% believed they had not contracted COVID-19, and the remaining 13.9% were unsure.

Another post-pandemic question concerned vaccination against COVID-19. The majority of respondents (82.5%) received the vaccine, while another 0.8% were considering it, and 16.8% did not receive a vaccine (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Post-pandemic question: “Did you get sick from COVID-19?”

Figure 2. Post-pandemic question: “Did you get vaccinated (with one, two, or three doses)?”

Discussion

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, rapidly evolved into a global crisis affecting nearly every aspect of life, precipitating widespread psychological distress (Sampogna et al. 2021). Beyond its medical implications, numerous studies have reported increases in anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress, and other mental health issues across diverse populations. The abrupt changes in daily routines, enforced social distancing, lockdown measures, and the loss of lives and livelihoods contributed to what many experts described as a parallel “mental health pandemic” (Bower et al. 2023; Chen et al. 2021). In this context, psychosocial support has emerged not only as beneficial but also as essential. While pandemics are not unprecedented in human history, COVID-19 represents the first to unfold within the context of globalization, digital connectivity, and widespread commodification – structural characteristics of contemporary society that have both accelerated viral transmission and intensified its psychological toll (Sawika et al. 2022). These are among the main features of modern society that have contributed to the spread of the pandemic and, at the same time, to its profound impact on the mental health of the general population. Even in the early aftermath of the WHO declaring a global pandemic in March 2020, there was awareness that the impact of the pandemic and the measures necessary to curtail it would inevitably result in psychological morbidity.

Our study, conducted 3 years after the pandemic started, provides valuable insights into the longer-term psychosocial consequences of the COVID-19 crisis, comparing self-reported mental health status, emotional distress, and perceived social support from 2020 to 2023. This is a critical moment for advancing mental health research as we strive to understand the mental health needs of the population and advocate for adequate resourcing to deliver quality mental healthcare in the post-pandemic period (Gavin et al. 2021).

One of our key findings indicates a significant improvement in general perceptions related to COVID-19, with a notable decrease in the proportion of respondents who associated flu-like symptoms with the virus or avoided thinking about it. This shift suggests a normalization of public perceptions and a reduction in the initial fear and uncertainty that characterized the early stages of the pandemic. This aligns with broader evidence that, although psychological distress was initially elevated, societies gradually adapted to the new reality (Sampogna et al. 2021). Several concerns have been reported among the general population, ranging from threats to personal and family safety to difficulties in receiving a prompt diagnosis of the infection, the use of containment measures that limit personal mobility, and the lack of effective treatments. The availability of vaccines has improved the situation significantly but has also been associated with a variety of partially unexpected complications, as well as generating new inequities (Privor-Dumm et al. 2023).

Regarding the demographic questions about children, it was shown that the presence of children significantly influenced pandemic-related stress, coping mechanisms, and mental health outcomes. Parents faced unique challenges during COVID-19, including managing children's remote schooling, balancing work-from-home with childcare responsibilities, concerns about children's health and development, and increased family tensions from prolonged confinement (Whaley and Pfefferbaum 2023). The age of children is particularly relevant because different developmental stages presented distinct challenges – caring for toddlers versus managing teenagers' educational and social needs required different coping strategies and generated varying stress levels (Aviles et al. 2024). Nevertheless, in their systematic review, Ng and Ng (2022) demonstrated that both children's and parents' mental health is at risk, and there is a critical need for tailored governmental interventions targeting children with internalizing and externalizing behaviors, particularly implementing health promotion and prevention strategies for lower socioeconomic status families who face heightened mental health risks in post-pandemic recovery policies.

Furthermore, our results demonstrate a significant improvement in mood, with a decrease in reported feelings of sadness, helplessness, despair, and hopelessness from 2020 to 2023. This suggests a recovery in emotional well-being over time, moving away from the heightened distress observed during the initial phases of the pandemic. This positive trend is further supported by the significant decrease in respondents reporting increased irritability and anger. These findings are consistent with emerging

literature suggesting that the acute phase of mental health challenges may subside as the immediate threat diminishes, although long-term effects can still persist among specific vulnerable groups (Bouza et al. 2023; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2023). The observation of this positive trend could be attributed to post-traumatic growth (Aulov et al. 2023). Lewis et al. (2022) demonstrated factors associated with post-traumatic growth: perceived social support, perceptions of the pandemic as traumatic, and higher psychological well-being. In line with this, Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) transactional theory of stress and coping has profoundly shaped pandemic-related psychological research, serving as the foundational framework for understanding how individuals cope with COVID-19 stressors (Biggs et al. 2017). Therefore, although the COVID-19 pandemic has had adverse effects on psychological well-being, it may concurrently offer pathways for beneficial change. Furthermore, we support the position paper by Moreno et al. (2020) on how mental healthcare should change as a consequence of the pandemic. They recommend that mental health delivery systems require sustainable, expert-designed adaptations that reduce healthcare disparities, with continuous outcome assessment determining which practices to expand or eliminate (Moreno et al. 2020).

The fear of contracting the virus or of a close one becoming infected significantly decreased in the post-pandemic period. This reduction in health-related anxiety likely contributes to the overall improvement in psychological well-being. This finding contrasts with initial concerns during the early pandemic that chronic anxiety and stress would lead to sustained mental health issues, as reported by Chen et al. (2021) and Lindert et al. (2021).

Our study also reveals a significant decrease in stress related to current or future financial problems linked to the pandemic, with a substantial increase in the proportion of respondents reporting no stress in this regard. This is a significant finding, as economic difficulties have been identified as a major contributor to psychological distress during the pandemic. The observed improvement in perceived financial stress in our Bulgarian sample suggests a potential economic recovery or adjustment to new economic realities in the country. This stands in contrast to earlier predictions that economic hardships, which have previously been shown to contribute to suicide risk, would lead to increased suicide rates following the COVID-19 pandemic (Chen et al. 2021). However, Oprea et al. (2020) investigated economic resilience across seven Eastern European countries following the 2008 crisis. They found that manufacturing sector size, services, public administration, entrepreneurship, and tertiary education are key determinants of regional economic resilience, with Bulgaria and Slovenia demonstrating the strongest resistance, while recovery patterns varied significantly across countries and regions. Our results also emphasize the observed resilience in our country, and we can also speculate on the broader concept of stress resilience development, especially in times of crisis, and how people “evolved” during and after the pandemic.

Additionally, our findings suggest that by 2023, many Bulgarian workers may have returned to traditional in-person work arrangements, potentially reflecting organizational policies that favor office presence, industry-specific requirements that do not accommodate remote work, or cultural preferences for face-to-face collaboration. This finding contradicts the popular narrative of a lasting “remote work revolution” and may indicate that the shift to online work was more temporary than anticipated, at least in the Bulgarian context.

Regarding social relationships, while family relationships largely remained unchanged, a notable decrease was observed in those who reported a sense of unity within their family. However, a significant positive change was seen in how respondents interacted with family and friends, transitioning from predominantly online communication to more frequent in-person meetings in the post-pandemic period. This trend reflects a reestablishment of pre-pandemic social behaviors and a potential reduction in perceived social isolation, which was a significant concern during lockdowns and a risk factor for developing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). The implementation of strict quarantine and lockdown measures disrupted established social networks. Prolonged exposure to loneliness has been identified as a key contributor to PTSD symptomatology. Overall, the pandemic profoundly affected the mental health of the population due to the widespread disruption of the social, economic, and psychological fabric of the global community (Chen et al. 2021).

Despite the observed improvements in various aspects of psychological well-being, our study found no significant change in the perceived need for professional psychological support. Approximately one-fifth of respondents in both surveys continued to express a need for such support, with a notable proportion in the post-pandemic sample actively seeking or considering mental healthcare. This sustained need for professional support, even as general distress subsides, underscores the importance of continued access to mental health services and acknowledges that for some individuals, the psychological impact of the pandemic may be more enduring. Data from previous public health crises and pandemics, as reported by Gavin et al. (2021), pointed to a likely peak in mental health problems that was predicted to occur after the initial wave of physical illness and may persist well beyond the resolution of the acute crisis.

Moreover, Hancheva and Bikovska (2025), who studied peripartum women, found that self-perceived social support was a protective factor against COVID-19-related depression and anxiety. The same authors also reported that reduced time spent on social media was associated with better psychological health.

Furthermore, our study observed a significant decline in unhealthy habits that became more prevalent during the pandemic, such as physical inactivity, overeating, cigarette smoking, and alcohol consumption. This suggests a return to healthier lifestyle choices as pandemic restric-

tions eased and daily routines normalized. In contrast, respondents in the post-pandemic period reported significantly increased engagement in hobbies, indicating a shift toward more adaptive coping mechanisms and activities promoting well-being.

Interestingly, the proportion of respondents who expressed a desire to be infected with the virus in order for the pandemic to “pass” more quickly significantly increased in the post-pandemic period. While seemingly counterintuitive, this might reflect growing frustration with prolonged uncertainty and a desire for resolution or a perception that the health risks associated with COVID-19 had diminished over time. Moreover, a significant decrease in self-reported sleep disturbances was observed in the post-pandemic period, which is another positive indicator of improved overall well-being. Insomnia was among the reported mental health burdens during the pandemic, as reported by Chen et al. (2021).

Finally, our study revealed that 16.8% of participants did not intend to get vaccinated. In contrast with our findings, Salama (2023) found that only 1% of pharmacy students in Jordan were not vaccinated. However, our study aimed to analyze the general population, which might differ from pharmaceutical students. Furthermore, Shen et al. (2025) found a decline in vaccine intention among the general population in the USA, comparing 2020 and 2022–2023.

Strengths and limitations of the study

Our study has a few limitations. First, it is an online survey that is prone to self-reporting bias. Furthermore, the second survey did not include the same individuals for pairwise comparisons. However, online data collection was the most appropriate research strategy during the pandemic. Moreover, online studies are mostly anonymous and do not allow researchers to study the same participants.

The study also has several strengths worth noting. We ensured three key methodological advantages that enhance its scientific rigor and contribution to pandemic mental health research. First, the longitudinal design with consistent methodology employed an identical survey instrument administered 3 years apart (2020 and 2023), enabling direct comparison of psychological responses from the acute pandemic phase to the post-crisis period and providing robust evidence for tracking genuine changes in mental health outcomes over time rather than relying on cross-sectional snapshots. Second, the research achieved substantial participation, with 1,020 respondents during the pandemic and 661 in the post-pandemic phase, totaling 1,681 participants. This enhances the statistical power of the findings and increases their generalizability to the broader Bulgarian adult population. Third, the rigorous survey development and validation process included thorough pilot testing with 20 individuals before distribution to ensure clarity, relevance, and comprehensibility of questions, while the anonymous electronic format encouraged honest responses on sensitive mental health

topics. The requirement to complete all fields maintained data integrity and completeness, collectively strengthening the reliability and validity of the finding.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our Bulgarian online survey provides a nuanced overview of the evolving psychosocial impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. Notably, the initial levels of fear, anxiety, and stress among respondents in 2020 decreased significantly by 2023. Moreover, a clear trend toward improved mood, reduced unhealthy habits, and increased social interaction was observed. However, the sustained need for professional psychological support highlights the complex and potentially long-lasting effects of such a global health crisis on mental well-being. These findings underscore the importance of ongoing monitoring and targeted, population-specific mental health interventions to address the diverse needs of the population in the aftermath of major crises.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, T.V. and H.B.; methodology, E.N.; software, L.T.; validation, E.N., K.G. and V.J., formal analysis, L.T.; investigation, D.G.; resources, V.I.; data curation, E.N.; writing – original draft preparation, T.V. and E.N.; writing – review and editing, L.T., K.G., V.J.; visualization, E.N.; supervision, T.V.; project administration, T.V.; funding acquisition, T.V. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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